

TG/DSC and kinetic parametrization of the combustion of agricultural and forestry residues

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ABSTRACT

The present paper discusses the data obtained from the thermogravimetric analysis and kinetic evaluation of seven different experimental solid biomasses representative of the Euroregion Galicia-North Portugal and commonly found in Europe. The samples comprised three raw, nonwoody biomasses and four additivated batches blended with kaolin and calcium carbonate. A TG-DSC analysis was performed on each sample under an oxidative atmosphere and three heating ratios, and the additives were found to increase the duration of the oxidation of carbon, its heat release, and displaced the reaction of volatile compounds to higher temperatures, while at the same time decreasing the peak heat emission caused by the volatiles up to a 40%. Three isoconversional methods, namely, Flynn-Wall-Ozawa, Kissinger-Akahira-Sunose and Friedman were utilized to determine the activation energy and pre-exponential factor of the fuels, both globally and at intervals during conversion, and the results were found to be similar among the three methods, with values ranging from 47.07 kJ/mol to 228.31 kJ/mol for conversion degrees between 0.1 and 0.9. Fuels mixed with the additives mentioned exhibited lower activation energy values than their raw counterparts, suggesting an enhancement of the combustion conditions.

1. Introduction

The equilibrium between providing sustainable and environmentally responsible energy and providing it at the most competitive price possible is one of the main challenges that the energy sector faces in the current global scenario. Policymakers at all levels are focusing their efforts on reducing the carbon footprints of their economies, taking this fact into account [1,2]. The utilization of new biomass feedstocks replacing traditional biomass and fossil fuels is a well-established trend in heat-generating appliances and has proven to be effective in reducing pollutant emissions during combustion [3–6]. Nevertheless, the rapid spread of these applications leads to greater pressure being exerted over forest resources [7], which are not homogeneous worldwide and thus not available everywhere at the same quality.

Therefore, the need for the diversification of biomass sources has promoted a significant number of studies centered around the idea of harnessing the energetic potential of a wide array of wastes generated not only in agriculture [8–11] but also in other industries [12–15]. This could also help overcome the transportation issues associated with biomass, given that, the further a production area is from the utilization

area, the more the low energetic density hinders the feasibility of the biomass utilization [16]. Nevertheless, the utilization of these fuels is not devoid of issues. The high ash and particulate matter yields of these alternative fuels are both compelling reasons for the development of technologies and strategies focused on their reduction and, given the opportunity, valorization [17].

A need for the expansion of knowledge about alternative biomasses implies a necessity for the determination of the characteristics of such new energy sources. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) provides the mass loss rate of a given substance when it is submitted to a heating cycle under a controlled atmosphere. This method is commonly used to assess certain physical and chemical properties of a given fuel, such as its reactivity, ash yield and activation energy, as well as to perform proximate analyses of fuel samples; the method is especially common in the fields of biomass and bioenergy. Numerous works have been published about this subject, such as one by A. Skreiberg et al. in which wood, coffee waste and glossy paper were investigated [18] and a study performed by L. Burhenne et al. [19] wherein the individual components of biomass were analyzed, among other research performed [20–23].

This type of analysis is often complemented with differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), which allows the recording of the heat flow into

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Abbreviations

A	Pre-exponential factor of the Arrhenius equation (min^{-1})
bp	Common broom pellet
E	Activation energy (kJ/mol)
$f(\alpha)$	Reaction model
FWO	Flynn-Wall-Ozawa method
$g(\alpha)$	Integrated form of the reaction model
gN2	Gorse pellet blended with 2% kaolinite
gN3	Gorse pellet blended with 2% CaCO ₃
gp	Gorse pellet
HS	Hard sinter
$k(T)$	Rate constant of the Arrhenius equation
KAS	Kissinger-Akahira-Sunose method
kN2	Kiwi pellet blended with 2% kaolinite
kN3	Kiwi pellet blended with 2% CaCO ₃

kp	Kiwi pellet
m0	Initial mass of the sample
MELT	Melted sinter
mf	Final mass of the sample
mt	Mass of the sample at a given time t
$p(u)$	Integrated form of the temperature
R	Universal gas constant
T	Temperature
TGA	Thermogravimetric analysis
TG-DSC	Thermogravimetric analysis-differential scanning calorimetry
WS	Weak sinter
XRF	X-ray fluorescence
α	Conversion degree
β	Heating ratio ($^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$)

or from a sample, thus offering very precise information about the temperatures at which chemical reactions take place [24–26]. When combined with kinetic models and methods such as the Flynn-Wall-Ozawa (FWO) method or the more robust Kissinger-Akahira-Sunose (KAS) method, the data obtained from TG-DSC analysis can be used to determine the kinetic parameter values of fuels, namely, their activation energy (E) and the pre-exponential factor (A) of the Arrhenius equation. These isoconversional methods assume that the entire process of reaction can be simplified to a single-step equation, thus removing the necessity of studying all the intermediate processes. R. Barzegar et al. [27] studied the kinetic parameters of lignite using three isoconversional methods, while M. P. González et al. [28] focused on olive, almond, coffee and cocoa wastes. Other authors have investigated the thermal properties of similar conventional and unconventional fuels [29,30]. These values are fundamental for simulation and design purposes, and therefore, the experimental research leading to them is of capital importance. As stated by Vyazovkin [31], kinetic data are essential to render a mathematical expression that describes the process. When these values are defined accurately, they allow for the replication of the original kinetics data as well as for the forecasting of process kinetics at different temperatures from those reached in the performed experiments.

In this study, the kinetic parameters of the combustion of seven experimental fuels are determined by means of a combined TG-DSC analysis and three common model-free methods, namely, FWO, KAS and Friedman. These isoconversional methods have been selected for their widespread use in kinetic research, and because they represent the two main groups of isoconversional methods according to their mathematical background, being FWO and KAS integral methods and Friedman a differential one, thus expanding the representativity of the data and offering a way to compare the results of the three methods. These fuels are obtained from agricultural and forestry residues commonly found in the Galicia-North Portugal Euroregion, more precisely from kiwi (*Actinidia deliciosa*) pruning, gorse (*Ulex europaeus*) and common broom (*Cytisus scoparius*). The origins of these fuels are of particular relevance because the research presented here derives from the Biomasa AP project [32], a scientific effort to link the two territories of the aforementioned Euroregion in a cross-border knowledge hub, but research on these three species is relevant worldwide given that two of them (gorse and broom) are considered as a common weed in most countries, while the third (kiwi) is a fruit tree native to southern China that nowadays is cultivated extensively in Europe, America and Oceania. For these reasons, the development of a systematic way to extract as much value as possible from the residues generated in the processing

Fig. 1. Galicia-North Portugal Euroregion and fuels utilized for this study.

Table 1
Fuel characteristics.

Fuel	Species	Kiwi	Kiwi 2%wt kaolin	Kiwi 2%wt CaCO ₃	Gorse	Gorse 2%wt kaolin	Gorse 2%wt CaCO ₃	Common broom
	ID	kp	kN2	kN3	gp	gN2	gN3	
Ultimate analysis ^a	N	1.01	0.77	0.78	1.40	1.26	0.68	1.36
	C	46.46	44.88	45.30	49.51	47.39	44.38	47.45
	H	6.04	6.13	6.22	6.96	7.82	7.63	6.88
	O ^b	46.48	48.23	47.70	42.13	43.53	47.31	44.31
Proximate analysis ^a	Moisture	10.16	9.43	9.24	9.80	7.16	7.42	8.11
	Volatiles	75.09	66.73	66.33	80.10	78.71	78.51	70.218
	Fixed carbon	22.64	27.36	26.99	17.86	17.32	17.24	26.55
	Ash	2.27	5.91	6.67	2.04	3.97	4.25	3.23
Fusibility	T < 1273 K	WS	WS	WS	HS	WS	WS	HS
	1273 K < T < 1373 K	WS	WS	WS	MELT	WS	WS	MELT
	1373 K < T < 1423 K	MELT	HS	MELT	MELT	MELT	HS	MELT
Heating Value	HHV (kJ/kg)	18757.70	17450.99	20415.62	18485.02	19444.50	19436.10	20023.00
	LHV (kJ/kg)	17435.30	16128.52	19093.16	17162.60	18122.00	18113.70	18700.60
Bulk density (kg/m ³)		610.90	572.40	644.60	504.60	568.10	528.80	n.a.

WS: weak sinter, easily reduced to dust by applying pressure HS: hard sinter, not easily crumbled and difficult to separate from the plate MELT: melted sinter, completely adhered to the plate, impossible to remove, n.a.: not available.

^a wt %, dry base.

^b calculated.

and elimination of these species is so relevant. Other research stemming from this very same project has already studied the kinetic behavior of raw kiwi- and gorse-derived pellets through the Arrhenius law [33]. To address the foreseeable issues with ash coalescence that solid fuels originating from nonwoody sources tend to present, two batches of additivated fuels were also created for kiwi and gorse fuels. The additives selected were calcium carbonate and kaolinite, as previous research has shown their high effectiveness in dealing with molten ash problems [34,35]. Mineral additives constitute a cost-effective strategy to deal with ashes that have a low fusion temperature, as they react with problematic substances, such as potassium or sodium, known to be the main causes of low melting points, and create compounds that are more stable when subjected to higher temperatures. Thus, the main objectives were to explore the influence of these additives on the combustion characteristics and kinetics of novel fuels, further developing the knowledge on mineral fuel additives and their effect on combustion, as not much literature regarding them exists, and to contribute a full data set containing all fuels and their variations obtained through three different methods.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Biomass feedstocks

Samples of biomass wastes gathered in the Galicia-North Portugal Euroregion (Fig. 1) were collected from local agricultural and forestry

industries and submitted to thermogravimetric analysis. The raw biomasses used were kiwi pruning (kp), gorse (gp) and common broom (bp). The fuels were received in the form of pellets and ground in an IKA MF 10 mill with impact heads and a 3-mm sieve prior to analysis in the TG/DTA apparatus. The fraction of biomass powder retained by the sieve was fed again to the inlet and ground further. As discussed in previous research, additives have proven to be a successful strategy to address the inconveniences created by the high ash yields of nonwoody biomass as well as the emission of particulate matter [36–39]. Thus, two of the feedstocks were used to create additivated fuels, namely, gorse with 2 wt % kaolinite (gN2), gorse with 2 wt% CaCO₃ (gN3) and kiwi with 2 wt% kaolinite (kN2) and kiwi with 2 wt% CaCO₃ (kN3). The inhomogeneity of the biomass fuels, especially those from non-woody origins such as the case, is a common issue that has been addressed here by grinding and mixing each feedstock until the maximum possible homogeneity had been reached. Other sources of compositional variability, such as the characteristics of the soil or the fertilizers used, are not a focus of this research and thus will not be addressed.

Table 1 lists information about the proximate, ultimate and fusibility analyses of the tested fuels. The structural elements of the biomasses (cellulose, hemicellulose and lignine) were not studied for this research. The ultimate analysis was performed in a Fisons Carlo Erba EA1108 microanalyzer according to the procedure of ISO 16948 and ISO 16994, while the ash content was determined by means of the methodology described in ISO 18122. These data show similar proportions of C, H, N and O in all fuels, and no other components were detected in proportions

Table 2
XRF ash analysis.

Fuel	Species	Kiwi	Kiwi 2%wt kaolin	Kiwi 2%wt CaCO ₃	Gorse	Gorse 2%wt kaolin	Gorse 2%wt CaCO ₃	Common broom
	ID	kp	kN2	kN3	gp	gN2	gN3	
Ash components [mg/kg]	Na	233	1743	1532	1825	263	349	902
	Mg	962	1083	793	1312	1209	1262	1179
	Al	336	2668	271	484	3110	1458	604
	Si	1013	7717	1137	2667	9375	5244	3485
	P	854	313	311	442	746	760	696
	S	49	830	705	1031	561	596	1167
	Cl	838	646	671	607	95	126	775
	K	7972	3338	2977	3334	6336	6196	4569
	Ca	4817	2816	2606	3989	7053	16,971	4286
	Ti	9	22	9	64	50	50	26
	Mn	7	401	278	514	83	66	790
	Fe	85	1044	407	1425	1035	836	1058
	Zn	41	45	43	83	92	80	69

Fig. 2. TGA/DTA-DSC apparatus employed for the tests.

over the detection limit of the device (0.03%). Furthermore, a proximate analysis showed the high amounts of ash created by all fuels; these amounts were even higher for the additivated fuels, as the additives themselves form portion of the ash after combustion. The fusibility analysis revealed that raw feedstocks are more prone to melting than those with additives, as was expected.

The ash composition was determined by means of a Siemens SRS3000 X-ray fluorescence (XRF) spectrometer, and the resulting data are provided in Table 2. The results from this technique show important amounts of sodium and potassium in the fuels, known to be directly related to fouling and slagging issues [40,41].

2.2. Thermogravimetric study of the samples

A SETARAM Labsys TGA/DTA-DSC apparatus, shown in Fig. 2, was employed to carry out the experiments on the seven biomasses. The experiments were performed under an oxidizing atmosphere (21% O₂, 79% N₂, provided by Praxair Inc.) and a constant flow rate of 50 ml/min. Three sets of tests were executed, applying a constant heat rate of 10, 20 and 30 °C/min from 20 to 900 °C to a sample of 10 ± 0.5 mg of biomass inside a 100-μl platinum crucible. For each set, a blank test was performed with an empty crucible to allow the baseline to be subtracted from the other tests. The apparatus was calibrated according to the instructions provided by the supplier.

The determination of the characteristic combustion parameters was possible through the analysis of an extensive data set obtained from the experimental tests. The raw data produced by the apparatus software were postprocessed to improve their quality. Not only was the mass reported in the blank tests subtracted from the mass gathered in the actual tests, but a filter was also applied to smooth the data and reduce the effect of the experimental noise on the overall curves. The filter applied to the whole set was a 0-degree Savitzky-Golay [42], and the number of points was adjusted to encompass 1% of the test time. Each

Table 3

Reaction models for solid-state reactions.

Reaction model	$f(\alpha)$	$g(\alpha)$
Power Law	$4 \cdot \alpha^{3/4}$	$\alpha^{1/4}$
Avrami-Erofeev	$4 \cdot (1-\alpha) \cdot [-\ln(1-\alpha)]^{3/4}$	$[-\ln(1-\alpha)]^{1/4}$
First-order reaction	$1-\alpha$	$-\ln(1-\alpha)$
Second-order reaction	$(1-\alpha)^2$	$(1/2) \cdot (1-\alpha)^{-2} \cdot (1/2)$

test, including the blanks, was performed thrice to ensure reproducibility, and the average standard error of the temperature measurements was 0.029.

2.3. Kinetic models

Research on the kinetics of reactions is of utmost importance in the fields of combustion and biomass fuels. The determination of the parameters governing these reactions is crucial to their understanding and plays a huge role in the modeling and design of biomass facilities. Numerous authors have attempted to model combustion kinetics over the years by means of global reaction models or the decomposition of these models into the individual contributions of each component [43–46]. These models have had mixed success in providing an accurate representation of the degradation of fuels, due in part to the difficulty of modeling a heterogeneous fuel composition through a mixture of model compounds [47–49]. Vyazovkin [50] argued that even if thermally stimulated reactions in the solid-state involve multiple steps, the reduction of complexity inherent to kinetic analysis still allows these techniques to describe the temperature dependence of the overall reaction rate and to produce consistent kinetic characteristics from both isothermal and nonisothermal data. These methods, and the parameters extracted from them, are useful for studying the behavior of the fuels but not necessarily in a mechanistic way. That is, the values obtained are comparable to each other and to those in the literature, resulting from the application of the same procedures, and are useful for determining the qualitative behavior of a fuel. However, they are not meant to explain the full complexity of the processes taking place in the reaction, given the huge simplifications made to perform the calculations.

A common approach to kinetic analysis is by means of model-free methods, a strategy that avoids the constraints related to the selection of a reaction model. This circumvents the need for the determination of the set of reactions taking place or their order. The most utilized model-free methods are the so-called isoconversional methods. The basis of isoconversional methods is the reduction of the chemical process to a general, single-step equation [51]:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k(T) \cdot f(\alpha) \quad (1)$$

where $k(T)$ is the rate constant, $f(\alpha)$ is the chosen reaction model and α represents the conversion degree. The term α can be calculated as

follows:

$$\alpha = \frac{m_0 - m_t}{m_0 - m_f} \quad (2)$$

where m_0 is the initial mass of the sample, m_f is the final mass of the sample after the test, and m_t is the mass at any given time. Several reaction models have been developed over the years, and some of them are listed in Table 3, but the goal of these methods is to reach an expression wherein the kinetic parameters can be extracted independently from the reaction model. The rate constant k and its temperature dependency are defined by the Arrhenius equation:

$$k(T) = A \cdot e^{-E/R \cdot T} \quad (3)$$

where A is the pre-exponential factor, E is the activation energy, R is the gas constant, and T is the temperature. Given that TG-DSC requires accurate temperature control, it is possible to assume an experiment in which the heating rate is constant and the following parameter can be defined:

$$\beta = \frac{dT}{dt} \quad (4)$$

The utilization of the last parameter in (1) led Vyazovkin and Wight [31,50,52] to suggest that no single activation energy governs the reaction and that step reaction kinetics should be considered. Incorporating (3) and (4) into (1) results in the following equation:

$$\beta \cdot \frac{d\alpha}{dT} = A \cdot e^{-E/R \cdot T} \cdot f(\alpha) \quad (5)$$

The above equation can be integrated and rearranged as follows:

$$\int_0^\alpha \frac{d\alpha}{f(\alpha)} = \frac{A}{\beta} \int_{T_0}^T e^{\frac{-E}{R \cdot T}} dT \quad (6)$$

Subsequently, the following expression is obtained:

$$g(\alpha) = \frac{A \cdot E}{\beta \cdot R} \cdot p(u) \quad (7)$$

where $g(\alpha)$ and $p(u)$ are the integrated forms of the reaction model and the temperature, respectively. The temperature integral $p(u)$ is represented by the following equation:

$$p(u) = \int_\infty^u -\frac{e^{-u}}{u^2} du \quad (8)$$

where

$$u = \frac{E}{R \cdot T} \quad (9)$$

The value of $p(u)$ is obtained via approximations that depend on the method applied to obtain the kinetic parameters. For the research presented in the current article, three different model-free methods were applied to the data resulting from the experimental tests performed.

By using Doyle's approximation of the temperature integral [53], the Flynn-Wall-Ozawa equation can be obtained [54,55]:

$$\ln(\beta) = \ln \frac{A \cdot E}{R \cdot g(\alpha)} - 5.331 - 1.052 \cdot \frac{E}{R \cdot T} \quad (10)$$

From this equation, the plotting of $\ln(\beta)$ vs. $1/T$ for each conversion degree and several heating ratios is fitted to a straight line. The slope of the line allows for the calculation of activation energy, and the pre-exponential factor A can be obtained from the y-intercept.

Later developments of the technique led to Coats and Redfern proposing another approximation of the temperature integral [56], allowing for a better approximation of the result and providing the basis for the development of an arguably more robust method named

Fig. 3. a) Relative and differential mass loss. b) Differential Scanning Calorimetry Influence of heating velocity on gorse fuel.

Kissinger-Akahira-Sunose (KAS) [57]:

$$\ln \frac{\beta}{T^2} = \ln \frac{A \cdot R}{E \cdot g(\alpha)} - \frac{E}{R \cdot T} \quad (11)$$

Similar to the case of FWO, a plot of $\ln(\beta/T^2)$ vs. $1/T$ fits a straight line whose slope results in the activation energy of the sample for each conversion degree.

A different approach was suggested by H. L. Friedman [58], resulting in the most widely utilized differential isoconversional method:

$$\ln \frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \ln[A \cdot f(\alpha)] - \frac{E}{R \cdot T} \quad (12)$$

From which a plot of $\ln(da/dt)$ vs. $1/T$ can be extracted, while E can be obtained from the slope of the plot and A from the intercept.

Flynn-Wall-Ozawa and Kissinger-Akahira-Sunose are integral model free methods [59] that utilize different approaches for the solving of the temperature integral, and as such their results are expected to remain similar at all stages. On the other hand, the Friedman differential approach is much more sensitive to the experimental noise of the data and the strategy to solve the differential equation, thus the data has to be appropriately filtered and prepared to minimize error. Nevertheless, some differences are to be expected between integral and differential methods due purely to the mathematics behind them. The three methods are widely utilized to assess the kinetics of solid fuels and experimental biofuels ([60,61]), and have proven to be reliable estimators of the potential of new substances as energy sources.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. TG-DSC data

Regarding the effects of the heating rates, Fig. 3 shows a comparison between the TG and DSC curves for raw gorse fuel and the three tested heating rates. It becomes evident that the higher the heating rate is, the

Fig. 4. a) Relative mass loss and differential mass loss. b) Differential Scanning Calorimetry Influence of additives in the kiwi fuels.

higher the temperature is at which a certain reaction takes place. This can be observed in the peak temperature at which volatiles are released, which occurs at 308 °C for 10 °C/min, at 318 °C for 20 °C/min and at 320 °C for 30 °C/min. On the same note, a lower heating rate favors the oxidation of the fuel components taking place over a smaller temperature interval than higher heating rates. Observing the release and reaction of volatiles, it stands clear that, for 10 °C/min, the heat release

starts at 240 °C up until 330 °C, while for 30 °C/min, the interval is 220–360 °C. This is due to the increased residence time in the cases studied with slower heating ratios [62,63].

A similar trend is observed for the oxidation of fixed carbon. While starting at similar temperatures of approximately 350 °C, the consumption of all the fixed carbon present in the fuel occurs at a lower temperature of 10 °C/min than for the other rates. As such, the combustion reaction stops at 610 °C for 10 °C/min, at 810 °C for 20 °C/min and at approximately 880 °C for 30 °C/min. These traits were also observed in the other fuels tested, with identical tendencies.

In Fig. 4, data from the 30 °C/min tests are shown for the three kiwi-derived fuels. The simultaneous analysis of TG and heat flow data versus temperature allows for the determination of the processes taking place in the samples and the extrapolation of the temperatures at which moisture and volatiles are released and at which combustion takes place. All three fuels lose approximately 5–10% of their mass between 20 and 120 °C, losses that can be attributed to the release of moisture. After that point, a sharp decline in mass, close to 40%, is detected at approximately 250 °C due to the release of volatile compounds, and another steadier decline can be seen from 350 °C onwards, caused by the reaction of fixed carbon with oxygen. Through the analysis of the heat flow of the sample, it can be noted that the fuels containing additives exhibit different behaviors than the raw kiwi pellets. In these modified fuels, the release of volatiles was less noticeable, and the heat flow originating in the oxidation of fixed carbon reached higher values and was maintained at higher temperatures (880–900 °C) than in the case of raw kiwi (830 °C). The results suggest that additives delay the release of volatiles while extending the oxidation of carbon to higher temperatures under the same heating ratio.

A further development of the information obtained in the tests can be observed in Fig. 5, wherein the conversion degrees of the three kiwi-derived fuels are shown relative to the temperature and at the corresponding heating rate at which the experiments were performed. Again, it is evident that a slower heating rate favors the reactions taking place at lower temperatures. In all of the fuels, the conversion advances at similar rates until a temperature of 350 °C is reached. At this point, the higher the heating ratio, the slower the conversion progresses. This effect is more noticeable for the fuel with the calcium carbonate additive, wherein an almost complete decoupling of the three curves is observed

Fig. 5. Conversion vs. temperature curves for a) kiwi fuel, b) kiwi with 2% wt. kaolin and c) kiwi with 2% wt. CaCO₃.

Table 4
Reaction intervals, peak temperatures and %TG loss for the fuels tested.

	Gorse			Gorse N2			Gorse N3			Kiwi			Kiwi N2			Kiwi N3			Broom			
	M	V	FC	M	V	FC	M	V	FC	M	V	FC	M	V	FC	M	V	FC	M	V	FC	
10 °C/ min	RI [°C]	30-150	175-365	365-600	30-150	190-370	370-610	30-150	190-370	370-605	30-140	190-340	360-570	30-170	190-360	360-590	30-150	190-360	360-590	30-170	190-360	360-590
	Peak	80	308	*	80	285	*	80	280	80	280	*	85	290	*	70	290	*	70	330	*	330
	Temp. [°C]	11	49	37	8	47	41	9	51	38	10	45	40	10	46	39	14	49	36	9	52	38
20 °C/ min	% TG loss	30-150	175-375	375-825	30-145	170-420	420-805	30-180	190-400	400-780	30-160	190-370	370-780	30-180	180-380	380-790	30-180	190-380	380-845	30-150	190-370	370-790
	Peak	83	318	*	80	320	*	90	290	*	80	290	*	80	300	*	80	320	*	80	330	*
	Temp. [°C]	8	46	34	8	54	35	9	48	41	9	42	34	10	52	36	8	50	39	7	43	44
30 °C/ min	% TG loss	30-150	175-395	395-900	30-150	150-390	390-900	30-180	180-400	400-900	30-175	175-380	380-860	30-175	175-390	390-890	30-175	175-400	400-900	30-150	190-390	390-900
	Peak	85	320	*	80	330	*	90	300	*	85	290	*	89	300	*	67	330	*	90	330	*
	Temp. [°C]	9	43	39	4	43	40	9	51	34	9	43	33	9	50	33	16	48	31	4	38	50

RI = Reaction Interval.

M = Moisture.

V = Volatiles.

FC = Fixed Carbon.

* = Temperature peak for FC can't be determined due to the prolonged reaction span.

(Fig. 5c). A partial separation is also detected in the data from the tests performed with the kaolin additive, most notably from the start until 200 °C and from 350 °C onwards. This suggests that the addition of the fuels exacerbates their response to an increase in the heating ratios.

Further information pertaining the behavior of the fuels under the experiments can be observed in Table 4, where previously discussed results are also gathered. In the case of raw, additive-free fuels, the observed temperature ranges for the release or reaction of moisture, volatiles and fixed carbon are similar to those observed in the literature for other waste fuels [64,65] and sewage sludge [66]. For the altered fuels, the effect of N2 additive is clear, as it displaces the peak temperature of the reactions to higher temperatures. For N3 additive this effect is not so clearly seen, as gorse reactions with the additive happen at lower, rather than higher temperatures. From the pure, unaltered fuels, broom fuel shows reaction peaks at the highest temperatures, while also having the lowest amount of mass loss due to moisture, as it was expected from the results of the proximate analysis.

3.2. Kinetic parameters

By applying the methods described in Section 2.3, Kinetic Models, plots of the adequate parameters versus the inverse of T were drawn, as seen in Fig. 6, and their slopes and intercepts were utilized to calculate the activation energy values and pre-exponential factors at each conversion step. The steps ranged from 0.1 to 0.9 to obtain sufficient data points for the set to be representative. The linearity study gathered data from the tests performed at 10, 20 and 30 °C/min for each fuel type.

The significance of the results can be observed in Table 5, where the average R² parameter is shown for every method and fuel tested. The R squared is calculated for every conversion degree and averaged in order to offer an overview of the correctness of the fitting of the model to the experimental data. From this analysis, it stands out that the fuels with additives showed a worse fit to the mathematical model, although for most fuels the results are well adjusted to the ideal straight line, taking into account the experimental error inherent to these measurements. An exceptional accuracy was detected in Kiwi fuel, showing high values of R squared, while the approximations used to solve the integral contained in the Friedman method resulted in the less accurate fits across all fuels. This suggests that FWO and KAS methods are more suited to this analysis with experimental solid fuels.

Tables 6–8 list the calculated values of each parameter and the average values. From these, it can be seen that activation energies range from 47.07 kJ/mol to 228.31 kJ/mol for the FWO method, from 45.43 kJ/mol to 229.38 kJ/mol for the KAS method and from 37.19 kJ/mol to 206.26 kJ/mol for the Friedman method. Fuels containing additives tend to show lower activation energies than their raw counterparts, suggesting that the inclusion of additives in the composition of the fuels enhances combustion, possibly by a catalyst effect produced by the metals present in the ashes. As the amount of ash is higher than that in commercial fuels and the ash is richer in metals, some reactions could be enhanced in this environment. Ash conglomerates formed during the reaction due to the low melting point of the ash, as suggested in a previous study [67], are not believed to have a great influence in this scenario, as the amount of fuel is very low. The results obtained agree with those shown in previous research on raw and torrefied fuels (in the range of 66.83–296.59 kJ/mol) [68] and on other experimental fuels, such as wheat bran (34.02–336.34 kJ/mol) or hazelnut shells (57.48–145.36 kJ/mol) [69]. Raw experimental fuels tend to have higher activation energies than commercial pellets or those produced from woody biomasses evaluated in the consulted literature, but the modified versions, including additives, perform better and show lower activation energies comparable to those of commercial feedstock in most cases.

The results of the pre-exponential factor are expressed as log₁₀(A) to present more comprehensive values, as values of A per se are harder to work with. The pre-exponential factors calculated for this research vary from 4.83 to 52.37, depending on the fuel type and the method utilized.

Fig. 6. Kinetic curves at different conversion degrees for a) KAS and b) FWO methods for common broom pellet.

Table 5
Average R squared parameter of the results.

	Average R ²						
	Gorse	Gorse N2	Gorse N3	Kiwi	Kiwi N2	Kiwi N3	Broom
FWO	0.77	0.53	0.42	0.92	0.82	0.96	0.68
KAS	0.69	0.42	0.34	0.89	0.74	0.86	0.62
Friedman	0.55	0.33	0.24	0.90	0.75	0.84	0.52

Great variation and high values were expected given the results of previous research on the topic [25,33,68–70]. The average activation energies of all fuel types are also represented in Fig. 7 in a bar graph for the sake of clarity and to facilitate comparisons; it is clear that the FWO and KAS methods offer very similar results, one deviating an average of 8.65% from the other. For the Friedman method, due to the different approaches taken to calculate the parameters, the deviations are more pronounced. The average difference of the parameters calculated with the Friedman and FWO methods reaches 14.33%, while the same difference for Friedman and KAS is 5.54%, albeit with a greater standard deviation than the FWO-KAS difference. Reductions in the activation energies caused by the additives are evident in the gp, gN2 and gN3 experiments and even more so in the kp and kN3 experiments. The three species of raw fuels, on their side, have very similar average activation energies, ranging from 120 to 180 kJ/mol. In accordance to the results

Table 6
Kinetic parameters of the fuels tested according to the FWO method.

Conversion	Flynn-Wall-Ozawa							Pre-exponential factor log ₁₀ (A) [log ₁₀ (min ⁻¹)]						
	Activation energy (kJ/mol)													
	Gorse	Gorse N2	Gorse N3	Kiwi	Kiwi N2	Kiwi N3	Broom	Gorse	Gorse N2	Gorse N3	Kiwi	Kiwi N2	Kiwi N3	Broom
	gp	gN2	gN3	kp	kN2	kN3	bp	gp	gN2	gN3	kp	kN2	kN3	bp
0.1	7.71	21.80	9.67	63.10	14.63	8.31	60.58	0.65	1.58	0.68	6.95	1.05	0.59	5.25
0.2	174.67	58.88	107.03	316.89	98.46	63.31	320.73	16.30	4.93	9.58	30.54	8.74	5.37	30.36
0.3	300.62	67.34	95.09	384.04	75.09	86.23	408.08	27.83	5.66	8.29	36.12	6.46	7.40	37.88
0.4	315.83	74.47	78.60	365.67	54.78	96.12	362.69	28.40	6.22	6.67	33.42	4.62	8.16	32.66
0.5	278.72	54.97	69.82	309.78	54.02	111.81	247.80	24.19	4.48	5.81	27.31	4.51	9.37	21.52
0.6	77.31	46.80	11.76	105.64	20.28	64.01	116.85	6.10	3.60	1.42	8.47	1.92	5.05	9.54
0.7	46.00	42.29	45.23	54.68	59.08	39.97	48.81	3.36	3.04	3.33	4.00	4.37	2.96	3.68
0.8	28.70	31.16	37.39	36.52	46.45	28.69	37.01	2.14	2.24	2.64	2.63	3.31	2.15	2.67
0.9	24.97	25.95	27.34	26.75	34.68	23.97	28.06	1.92	1.96	2.03	2.05	2.55	1.91	2.11
Average	139.39	47.07	53.55	184.79	50.83	58.05	181.18	12.32	3.75	4.49	16.83	4.17	4.78	16.19

observed with the R squared parameter in the regression data, FWO and KAS activation energy values show a similar standard deviation and standard error of respectively 3.76 and 1.25 for FWO and 3.99 and 1.33 for KAS. Friedman results show a higher proportion of variability, with standard deviation on 12.86 and standard error on 4.29.

4. Conclusions

The present study aimed to determine the kinetic parameters of seven types of biomasses that are currently underutilized or considered waste as well as the effects of additives on these parameters. The raw biomasses were selected from among the most common types of residues generated by the silvicultural and agricultural industries in the Galicia-North Portugal Euroregion. Their potential for replacing fossil fuels and woody biomass were taken into consideration in their selection, and the inherent problems derived from their combustion, such as the generation of high amounts of slagging, were also contemplated; thus, batches of fuels blended with additives were created as well. TGA/DSC analyses were performed on each fuel type at different heating ratios under an oxidative atmosphere to gather thermal and mass loss data, and three different isoconversional methods, Flynn-Wall-Ozawa, Kissinger-Akai-hira-Sunose and Friedman, were used to extract the activation energy and pre-exponential factors from the raw data. The results show a high degree of convergence between the methods, and the values are found to be in the range of those reflected in the consulted literature. Friedman's

Table 7
Kinetic parameters of the fuels tested according to the KAS method.

Conversion	Kissinger-Akahira-Sunose							Pre-exponential factor $\log_{10}(A)$ [$\log_{10}(\text{min}^{-1})$]						
	Activation energy (kJ/mol)													
	Gorse	Gorse N2	Gorse N3	Kiwi	Kiwi N2	Kiwi N3	Broom	Gorse	Gorse N2	Gorse N3	Kiwi	Kiwi N2	Kiwi N3	Broom
	Gp	gN2	gN3	kp	kN2	kN3	bp	gp	gN2	gN3	kp	kN2	kN3	bp
0.1	0.80	14.43	2.05	59.33	13.04	1.44	55.24	-1.89	0.61	-1.45	7.22	0.54	-1.68	5.31
0.2	174.72	52.66	103.49	324.39	102.78	57.55	328.25	16.94	4.55	9.78	31.71	9.69	5.09	31.53
0.3	306.87	61.20	90.58	394.71	78.00	81.28	419.84	28.72	5.17	8.14	37.23	6.92	7.16	39.03
0.4	322.55	68.39	72.86	375.09	57.44	91.35	371.78	29.14	5.64	6.15	34.30	4.70	7.83	33.52
0.5	283.13	47.45	63.26	315.94	56.58	107.53	250.63	24.66	3.45	5.01	27.88	4.41	9.02	21.89
0.6	70.40	37.84	1.39	100.37	23.72	56.50	111.22	5.21	2.20	-1.99	7.88	1.06	4.00	8.97
0.7	36.02	31.71	35.44	45.45	56.11	29.82	39.36	1.73	1.29	1.70	2.57	3.50	1.20	2.14
0.8	16.05	18.50	25.99	25.00	35.77	16.45	25.29	-0.29	-0.10	0.59	0.54	1.51	-0.24	0.58
0.9	10.53	11.46	13.76	13.09	18.53	9.92	14.13	-1.00	-0.92	-0.69	-0.71	-0.12	-1.04	-0.62
Average	135.67	38.18	45.43	183.71	49.11	50.21	179.53	11.47	2.43	3.02	16.51	3.58	3.48	15.82

Table 8
Kinetic parameters of the fuels tested according to the Friedman method.

Conversion	Friedman							Pre-exponential factor $\log_{10}(A)$ [$\log_{10}(\text{min}^{-1})$]						
	Activation energy (kJ/mol)													
	Gorse	Gorse N2	Gorse N3	Kiwi	Kiwi N2	Kiwi N3	Broom	Gorse	Gorse N2	Gorse N3	Kiwi	Kiwi N2	Kiwi N3	Broom
	gp	gN2	gN3	kp	kN2	kN3	bp	gp	gN2	gN3	kp	kN2	kN3	bp
0.1	23.62	49.56	32.87	78.72	36.67	11.79	110.15	1.20	3.80	2.11	8.00	2.58	-0.23	10.01
0.2	214.92	72.25	95.32	347.16	106.45	137.65	387.43	19.72	5.84	8.16	32.59	9.24	11.70	35.87
0.3	313.11	81.70	82.66	392.50	64.57	98.44	437.51	28.09	6.55	6.73	35.76	5.11	7.90	39.38
0.4	327.52	47.80	73.93	359.32	29.25	132.48	358.56	28.43	3.30	5.73	31.66	1.79	10.65	31.21
0.5	126.00	14.99	10.66	222.19	38.32	179.99	149.65	9.79	0.09	-0.05	18.32	2.36	14.50	12.13
0.6	0.27	13.18	4.94	38.98	20.13	45.77	77.11	-1.17	-0.20	-0.84	1.94	0.48	2.47	5.12
0.7	2.37	0.44	3.35	9.36	19.07	43.74	3.42	-1.03	-1.12	-0.90	-0.46	0.37	1.86	-0.92
0.8	1.55	1.58	6.50	2.99	4.76	31.29	0.80	-0.96	-0.93	-0.66	-0.84	-0.57	0.91	-1.00
0.9	51.10	53.25	1.73	33.51	36.80	27.40	34.99	1.61	1.96	-1.10	0.55	0.82	0.90	0.64
Average	117.83	37.19	34.66	164.97	39.56	78.73	173.29	9.52	2.14	2.13	14.17	2.46	5.63	14.71

Fig. 7. Activation energies of the fuels tested according to the three methods utilized.

method showed the greatest divergence from the other two, which was expected due to the utilization of instantaneous values in the calculations, making this method highly sensitive to experimental noise, though an effort to smooth the data was made. This clearly sets the stage for further work on improving the reliability of the method, with the increasing of the repetitions being a reasonable approach to eliminate the experimental noise and variations, which could help overcome the limitations of the method. Furthermore, if a higher number of heating

rates were to be utilized, the data could be better fitted to the mathematical model, although a reasonably good fit was already achieved in this research for most fuels tested.

The addition of inorganic substances to the fuels resulted in a decrease in activation energy. These additives proved in the past to be an appropriate strategy to deal with slagging issues, and their benefits to combustion seem not to be limited to that in light of the presented results. The reduction in activation energy suggests an easier to initiate,

more reliable reaction that could lead to more efficient combustion. The results obtained herein can be interpreted as favoring the use of additives in alternative solid fuels, as their performances are improved with respect to their raw counterparts. It is also believed that the kinetic data will prove useful in future modeling and simulations of combustion facilities and increase the body of knowledge on alternative solid biomass fuels. A detailed study on further improvements of the experimental fuels, such as other mineral additives or pretreatments and transformations of the fuel, such as torrefaction or pyrolyzation, are recommended in future research as to determine this additives performance on a global scale.

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